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This manuscript was submitted on 21 March 2023 for peer-review and publication in *Statistics in Medicine*.

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March 21, 2023

Short title: Confidence limits for a proportion

Data availability statement: The data that support the findings of this study were generated by simulation software that is available from the author on reasonable request.

Abstract

The estimation of the binomial proportion is one of the most basic tasks in medical statistics. Existing confidence intervals for the proportion can show a lack of symmetry in the probability of non-coverage in the upper and lower tails. This means that the individual confidence limits are not necessarily suitable for one-sided analyses, for example, in one-tailed hypothesis tests. This paper describes modifications to the limits of the Wilson interval for greater accuracy: a method of moments is applied with the first and *third* moments to improve the accuracy of the approximation to the relevant binomial tail probability. Optimality criteria are discussed, and the method is tuned accordingly. The method involves the solution of only a quadratic equation, and explicit expressions for the limits are only slightly more complicated than the equations for the Wilson interval. The focus throughout is on one-sided analysis, but the limits can be used to form an interval. However, if the only performance criterion relates to the two-sided question then the Wilson interval performs as well.

Keywords: binomial, Bernoulli, confidence limit, method of moments, proportion

1 Introduction

One of the most basic tasks in statistical inference is the estimation of the probability parameter of a Bernoulli or binomial distribution, π . Being a problem of estimation, the frequentist statistician is likely to seek a confidence interval with random limits L and U such that $\Pr(L \leq \pi \leq U)$ is at least as high as the stated figure, say $1 - 2\alpha$, or approximately so. Usually, much less interest would be placed on the symmetry of non-coverage, i.e., the relative sizes of the contributing probabilities of non-coverage, $\Pr(L > \pi)$ and $\Pr(U < \pi)$. Yet, for many practical problems, only a single-sided inference of the form “ $\pi > a$ ” or “ $\pi < b$ ” is required, which would imply that the appropriate task is the formation of an individual confidence limit with coefficient $1 - \alpha$. In this paper, we address this one-sided problem directly and propose a procedure for the accurate calculation of an individual confidence limit. In medical statistics, directed interventions are developed only to *improve* people’s health, so such interventions are best assessed using ‘one-tailed’ reasoning and

logic. This permits the use of a sample size smaller by 20–25% than in a corresponding two-tailed analysis, e.g., [1].

Section 2 outlines well-regarded confidence intervals for π and emphasizes the quality of the Wilson interval in particular. Section 3 shows how a variation on the standard *method of moments* can be used to develop new confidence limits, while Section 4 uses this to describe a basic pair of limits and a proposed pair of limits. Section 5 discusses optimality criteria and, in response, Section 6 gives an analysis of the performances of the various limits. Section 7 concludes. The Appendix describes Wilson’s argument and considers the name of his interval. Throughout the paper, the concept of ‘symmetry’ refers to symmetry of non-coverage, not symmetry about the point estimate.

2 Existing intervals

Suppose a confidence interval is required for a proportion π when a random number of successes X is observed in n independent trials. Define

$$P \equiv \frac{X}{n}$$

and let $z \equiv z_\alpha$ be the $(1 - \alpha)$ -quantile of the standard normal distribution, e.g. $z_{0.025} \approx 1.96$. The traditional $(1 - 2\alpha) \times 100\%$ interval based on a normal approximation has limits

$$L_{\text{trad}}, U_{\text{trad}} \equiv P \pm z\sqrt{P(1 - P)/n}.$$

This has come to be known as the ‘Wald’ interval because it is formed using a general principle that Wald employed elsewhere. It is now regarded as being inappropriate for use with small samples, e.g., [2, 3]. We will call it the ‘traditional interval’.

In obtaining each limit, the traditional interval employs the standard deviation that is applicable at the point estimator P . In contrast, the interval of Wilson [4] (W) uses the standard deviations applicable at the limits themselves, thus inverting hypothesis tests at these limits. Consequently, the limits are

$$L_W, U_W \equiv \frac{P + c \pm \sqrt{2cP(1 - P) + c^2}}{1 + 2c} \quad c \equiv \frac{z^2}{2n}.$$

(So this modification moves the centre of the interval closer to 0.5). This interval is greatly superior to the traditional interval in terms of coverage. It has been called the Wilson ‘score’ interval, but Wilson’s derivation of it was based on an intuitive principle, not the idea of a score statistic, which is irrelevant to its rationale. This is made clear in the Appendix, which reproduces Wilson’s argument.

Having noticed that the Wilson interval is centred on the point

$$\dot{P} \equiv \frac{X + (z^2/2)}{n + z^2},$$

Agresti and Coull [5] proposed the simple interval with limits

$$L_{AC}, U_{AC} \equiv \dot{P} \pm z\sqrt{\dot{P}(1 - \dot{P})/(n + z^2)}.$$

The Agresti-Coull (AC) interval is wider than the Wilson interval, but the effect is not great. Its simplicity and accuracy appear to make it extremely useful, especially in education [6]. Agresti and Coull observed that Wilson had been aware of this idea of adding two successes and two failures as pseudo-data for point estimation in the $\pm 2\sigma$ situation.

Brown, Cai and DasGupta [2] highlight the inadequacies of the traditional interval and the inappropriateness of qualifications placed on its use in standard texts. They recommend three intervals, these being the Wilson interval, the Agresti-Coull interval and an interval that takes a ‘prior distribution’ for π to be the standard beta distribution with parameters $1/2$ and $1/2$, which is the Jeffrey’s prior (JP). This interval has lower limit $L_{JP} = 0$ when $X = 0$ and upper limit $U_{JP} = 1$ when $X = 1$, and otherwise the limits L_{JP} and U_{JP} are the α and $1 - \alpha$ quantiles of the beta distribution with parameters $X + 1/2$ and $n - X + 1/2$. These limits are easily calculated using standard software, and approximations are available [2, Section 3.1.3]. In this context, the JP interval might be said to accord with an ‘objective Bayesian’ view and with the concept of ‘logical probability’, where a probability distribution about a constant is said to properly and completely describe rational belief in response to a certain set of information. This use of probability has recently been shown to lead to a logical contradiction [7, 8, 9], which renders it untenable as a scientific concept. (The relevant result described in those references is noteworthy: the combination of unique probability distributions said to correspond to disjoint sets of information about the same unknown admits no unique solution, so the essential premise of ‘logical probability’ must be unsound.)

2.1 Room for improvement

Newcombe [10] examined the performances of 11 different methods shortly before the publication of the Agresti-Coull interval. Of those 11 methods, the Wilson interval could be preferred (Method 3 in [10]). It is simple to calculate and, for $2\alpha = 0.05$, has coverage close to 95% when there is averaging over many settings of n and π . However, one area of potential improvement is in its degree of symmetry. For example, at the value of π where the coverage probability takes its minimum value, all the intervals corresponding to untrue inferences lie fully beyond π , as viewed from the mid-point 0.5. So the motivation for this paper is the development of more symmetric limits, which will mean an interval that is located ‘closer to 0.5’.

The requirement for symmetric coverage is not usually prioritized, but if a 95% interval is constructed to be symmetric then the quotation of a 95% interval $[a, b]$ is equivalent to the quotation of three intervals, the others being the 97.5% semi-infinite intervals $[a, \infty)$ and $(-\infty, b]$. We then obtain three useful inferences for the price of one. Consequently, this paper provides simple alternatives to the individual confidence limits that are found in the existing intervals, especially for the case where only one limit is relevant, as when a one-tailed hypothesis test is carried out by inverting a confidence procedure. Our analysis places the focus on ‘single-sided’ statistical inference, which (in the author’s opinion [11]) is appropriate in the vast bulk of applied medical research. The use of a pair of limits as a finite interval should only be a secondary consideration.

There has been relatively little previous attention on the generation of individual limits for the binomial proportion π . The only paper sighted with this emphasis is that of Hall [12] (H), who uses asymptotic theory to indicate that the lower limit

$$L_H^* \equiv P - z\sqrt{P(1-P)/n} - \frac{1+P}{3n} + \frac{(1-2P)z^2}{3n}$$

obeys $\Pr(L_H^* \leq \pi) = 1 - \alpha + O(n^{-1})$. The constrained form of this limit, $L_H \equiv \max\{L_H^*, 0\}$, will be one of the limits studied in this paper.

3 Normal approximations for accuracy with individual tails

Let x and $p \equiv x/n$ be the realizations of X and P . So p is the point estimate of π . Also, let ℓ and u denote the realizations of the limits L and U .

The traditional, Wilson and Agresti-Coull intervals each involve the approximation of binomial distributions by normal distributions with the same first and second moments. Each of these

intervals may be understood to utilize one normal distribution centred on the lower confidence limit and a second normal distribution centred on the upper confidence limit, with the relevant tails being the upper and lower tails, respectively. The traditional and Agresti-Coull methods approximate a single binomial distribution with probability parameter equal to p , so they both involve normal distributions with the same variance. In contrast, the Wilson method approximates two binomial distributions with probability parameters equal to the two limits, so the Wilson method involves normal distributions with different variances. In every case, the relevant normal distribution is identified by matching its first and second moments to those of the appropriate binomial distribution, as in a ‘method of moments’.

Figure 1 illustrates some of these ideas for $n = 30$, $x = 6$ and $\alpha = 0.05$. Figure 1(a) shows (schematically) the binomial distributions that would be involved if carrying out a procedure using ‘exact’ probabilities, (as in the Clopper-Pearson approach [10]). Figure 1(b) shows the normal approximations to these distributions when constructing the traditional interval: both normal distributions have variance $p(1 - p)/n$. Figure 1(c) shows the normal approximations to the distributions for the Wilson interval: the normal distributions have different variances, the result being much closer approximation to the relevant binomial distributions. In each of the six distributions presented, a single tail is relevant, and the tail probability is $\alpha = 0.05$.

Figure 1: Three constructions for inference on π with $\alpha = 0.05$ when $n = 30$ and $x = 6$. So $p = 0.2$. The dashed lines show the probability mass/density functions used to obtain the tail probabilities. (a) Confidence limits ℓ and u corresponding to an ‘exact’ construction, (e.g., Clopper-Pearson). (b) Limits of traditional confidence interval, $\ell = \ell_{\text{trad}}$ and $u = u_{\text{trad}}$. (c) Limits of Wilson confidence interval, $\ell = \ell_{\text{W}}$ and $u = u_{\text{W}}$.

Figure 1 supports the conclusion that Wilson's approach improves on the traditional approach both practically and conceptually. But although Wilson's algorithm acknowledges that there are two different binomial distributions involved, it does not treat these distributions as being asymmetric, because it continues to match the first and *second* moments. In this section, we take Wilson's approach but match the first and third moments instead, in what might be called a 'method of alternative moments'. The underlying idea is that using an alternative pair of moments will improve the quality of the match in one tail — so that an approximation designed specifically for use in that tail would improve on a standard approximation that does not distinguish between tails. Although the method involves third moments, the limits of the interval obtained are calculable from a quadratic equation, and they are able to be given simply and explicitly.

3.1 A method of alternative moments

As usual, let μ'_r denote the r th moment of a random variable about the origin and let μ_r denote the r th central moment. Then the first and third moments about a suitable point $hn\pi$ are

$$\begin{aligned} m_1 &= \mu'_1 - hn\pi \\ m_3 &= m_1^3 + 3m_1\mu_2 + \mu_3. \end{aligned}$$

The random variable X has the binomial distribution with parameters n and π . So the first and third moments of X about $hn\pi$ are

$$\begin{aligned} m_1(X, h) &= n\pi(1 - h) \\ m_3(X, h) &= [n\pi(1 - h)]^3 + [3n\pi(1 - h)]n\pi(1 - \pi) + n\pi(1 - \pi)(1 - 2\pi). \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The first and third moments of a normal variable with mean μ and variance σ^2 about $hn\pi$ are

$$\begin{aligned} m_1(\mu, \sigma^2, h) &= \mu - hn\pi \\ m_3(\mu, \sigma^2, h) &= (\mu - hn\pi)^3 + 3(\mu - hn\pi)\sigma^2. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Matching these moments gives

$$\mu = n\pi \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma^2 = n\pi(1 - \pi) + \frac{(1 - \pi)(1 - 2\pi)}{3(1 - h)} \quad h \neq 1. \quad (4)$$

So, for a suitable choice of h , the distribution of X might be approximated by a normal distribution with mean and variance given by (3) and (4).

Based on this approximation, a nominal *lower* $1 - \alpha$ confidence limit for π is the value of π for which a normal variable with mean and variance given by (3) and (4) has $(1 - \alpha)$ -quantile equal to X . So, to find this lower limit, we seek to solve the equation

$$X = n\pi_* + z\sqrt{n\pi_*(1 - \pi_*) + \frac{(1 - \pi_*)(1 - 2\pi_*)}{3(1 - h)}} \quad (5)$$

for π_* . Set

$$b \equiv \frac{1}{3n(1 - h)}. \quad (6)$$

The solution is the smaller value of π_* satisfying the quadratic equation

$$(1 + 2c - 4cb)\pi_*^2 + (6cb - 2P - 2c)\pi_* + (P^2 - 2cb) = 0$$

where, as earlier, $c = z^2/(2n)$. The solution is

$$L \equiv \frac{P + c - 3cb - Y}{1 + 2c - 4cb}$$

with

$$Y \equiv \sqrt{2cP(1 - P) + 2cb(1 - P)(1 - 2P) + c^2(1 - b)^2}.$$

Thus L is a nominal lower $1 - \alpha$ confidence limit for π . The limit depends on h , which can be chosen for good performance but which must be chosen by a predetermined procedure. The limit differs from the Wilson limit in that $b \neq 0$. For fixed h , as $n \rightarrow \infty$, the limit becomes the traditional, Wilson and Agresti-Coull limits.

The flexibility with h is a noteworthy by-product of using an alternative pair of moments. If we had matched the first and second moments instead then we would have used the equations

$$\begin{aligned} m_2(X, h) &= \{n\pi(1 - h)\}^2 + n\pi(1 - \pi) \\ m_2(\mu, \sigma^2, h) &= (\mu - hn\pi)^2 + \sigma^2, \end{aligned}$$

instead of (1) and (2), which would have led to the equation $\sigma^2 = n\pi(1 - \pi)$ instead of (4). The result does not depend on h , so there is no flexibility when matching the lowest two moments. A general principle is apparent: when an approximating distribution has k parameters, matching the k moments of lowest order leads to results that do not depend on the choice of origin, but matching an alternative set of k moments gives results that do depend on the choice of origin, thus permitting a choice for good performance.

An analogous upper limit U could be found by solving the same problem with $n - X$ replacing X and then subtracting the limit from 1. The value of h used in the calculation of the upper limit could be different, so b and Y could also be different.

4 Explicit procedures

This section gives explicit procedures for two choices of h . The first procedure uses $h = 0$, so the moments matched are moments about the origin. The second procedure is slightly more complicated, but performance is improved and this is the procedure finally proposed. Before that, however, we consider the misleading idea that a confidence limit can lie in an unfeasible region.

The feasible interval for π is $[0, 1]$. We see that as π_* approaches 0, the radical in (5) approaches the non-zero quantity $\sqrt{1/[3(1 - r)]}$, meaning that when X/z is sufficiently small there is no positive solution to (5). In that case, the solution would be negative and outside the feasible region. Such difficulties are avoided by applying bounds to set the limits in the feasible region $[0, 1]$, which is a natural step that utilizes information available outside the ‘model’. It was implied above that the goal was to solve (5) for π_* . But this mathematical task misrepresents the inferential problem: the result actually sought is the set of all feasible values of π_* for which

$$X - n\pi_* \leq z \sqrt{n\pi_*(1 - \pi_*) + \frac{(1 - \pi_*)(1 - 2\pi_*)}{3(1 - h)}},$$

because this is the set of parameter values deemed consistent with the data. The confidence limit is just the smallest of these values.

(When such a problem is expressed in this way, it becomes apparent that the idea that a confidence procedure can return a negative raw limit for a positive parameter is irrelevant: the limit would be the answer to the wrong question. A negative raw limit is not something to be embarrassed by. Rather, it is an opportunity to educate a client as to the actual meaning of a confidence

interval. See Willink [13, Ch. 15] for a discussion of analogous issues when sampling from a normal distribution with small mean known to be positive.)

4.1 The basic procedure: $h = 0$

When applied with $h = 0$, the procedure involves setting

$$\begin{aligned} c &\equiv \frac{z^2}{2n} \\ b_0 &\equiv \frac{1}{3n} \\ Y_0 &\equiv \sqrt{2cP(1-P) + 2cb_0(1-P)(1-2P) + c^2(1-b_0)^2} \end{aligned}$$

and writing the nominal $1 - \alpha$ lower limit for π as

$$L_0 \equiv \max \left\{ 0, \frac{P + c - 3cb_0 - Y_0}{1 + 2c - 4cb_0} \right\}. \quad (7)$$

By symmetry, the upper limit for π is found by interchanging P and $1 - P$, forming the lower limit and then subtracting this limit from 1. Thus, we calculate

$$\begin{aligned} Z_0 &\equiv \sqrt{2cP(1-P) + 2cb_0P(2P-1) + c^2(1-b_0)^2} \\ U_0 &\equiv \min \left\{ 1 - \frac{1 - P + c - 3cb_0 - Z_0}{1 + 2c - 4cb_0}, 1 \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging gives the nominal $1 - \alpha$ upper limit for π as

$$U_0 \equiv \min \left\{ \frac{P + c - cb_0 + Z_0}{1 + 2c - 4cb_0}, 1 \right\}. \quad (8)$$

The expressions in (7) and (8) differ in the signs and detail of the terms $-Y_0$ and $+Z_0$ and in the coefficients of the product cb_0 in the numerators. The quantities c and b_0 are small, so the departures of the limits from the point estimator P are chiefly described by the terms $-Y_0$ and $+Z_0$.

4.2 The proposed procedure

Now we consider the use of the method with $h \neq 0$, where the moments being matched are not taken about the origin. Note that h does not need to be a constant: it is sufficient that h is set by an explicit procedure stated prior to observation of the data. So h could be the realization of an observable random variable. Thus, in the calculation of the lower limit we replace h by a random variable $f(X, n, \alpha)$ and in the calculation of the upper limit we replace h by a random variable $f(n - X, n, \alpha)$. This means replacing the constant b introduced in (6) by random variables $B \equiv b_0/[1 - f(X, n, \alpha)]$ and $D \equiv b_0/[1 - f(n - X, n, \alpha)]$.

It turns out that performance is better for some positive settings of $f(\cdot, n, \alpha)$ than for $h = 0$. The proposed setting was chosen after careful consideration of what constitutes ‘good performance’. The ideas underlying the analysis are described in Section 5, and the levels of performance of the limits are compared in Section 6. After some experimentation, it was found that a suitable function was $f(X, n, \alpha) = L_0^{0.25+15\alpha}$, meaning that $f(n - X, n, \alpha) = (1 - U_0)^{0.25+15\alpha}$. (So the exponent is equal to 1 when $\alpha = 0.05$.) In this way, these procedures take the basic new limits L_0 and U_0 as intermediate, tuning, variables.

The method utilizes the third moment in the matching process, so the method with these settings will be called the M3 method, and the limits will be denoted L_{M3} and U_{M3} . The limits are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
B &\equiv \frac{1}{3n(1 - L_0^{0.25+15\alpha})} \\
Y &\equiv \sqrt{2cP(1 - P) + 2cB(1 - P)(1 - 2P) + c^2(1 - B)^2} \\
L_{M3} &\equiv \max \left\{ 0, \frac{P + c - 3cB - Y}{1 + 2c - 4cB} \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
D &\equiv \frac{1}{3n[1 - (1 - U_0)^{0.25+15\alpha}]} \\
Z &\equiv \sqrt{2cP(1 - P) + 2cDP(2P - 1) + c^2(1 - D)^2} \\
U_{M3} &\equiv \min \left\{ \frac{P + c - cD + Z}{1 + 2c - 4cD}, 1 \right\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

4.3 Examples

Tables 1 and 2 present lower and upper limits for various n and x for $\alpha = 0.01$. In keeping with the theme of one-tailed or ‘one-sided’ inference that underlies this paper, we consider the lower and upper limits separately.

n	x	p	ℓ_{trad}	ℓ_{W}	ℓ_{AC}	ℓ_{JP}	ℓ_{H}	ℓ_0	ℓ_{M3}
90	29	0.32	0.208	0.221	0.220	0.217	0.210	0.220	0.220
90	61	0.68	0.563	0.556	0.556	0.557	0.550	0.556	0.556
40	4	0.10	-0.010	0.034	0.025	0.027	0.017	0.030	0.028
40	36	0.90	0.790	0.738	0.730	0.753	0.738	0.739	0.743
19	2	0.11	-0.059	0.024	0.007	0.015	0.000	0.013	0.011
19	17	0.89	0.731	0.638	0.621	0.661	0.623	0.639	0.646
12	1	0.08	-0.102	0.012	-0.015	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.000
12	11	0.92	0.731	0.586	0.559	0.617	0.553	0.587	0.595

Table 1: Realized lower 99% confidence limits in example situations

n	x	p	u_{trad}	u_{W}	u_{AC}	u_{JP}	u_{H}	u_0	u_{M3}
90	29	0.32	0.437	0.444	0.444	0.443	0.450	0.444	0.444
90	61	0.68	0.792	0.779	0.780	0.783	0.790	0.780	0.780
40	4	0.10	0.210	0.262	0.270	0.247	0.262	0.261	0.257
40	36	0.90	1.010	0.966	0.975	0.973	0.983	0.970	0.972
19	2	0.11	0.269	0.362	0.379	0.339	0.377	0.361	0.354
19	17	0.89	1.059	0.976	0.993	0.985	1.000	0.987	0.989
12	1	0.08	0.269	0.414	0.441	0.383	0.447	0.413	0.405
12	11	0.92	1.102	0.988	1.015	0.995	1.000	1.000	1.000

Table 2: Realized upper 99% confidence limits in example situations

Brown, Cai and DasGupta [2, Section 1] write that the Wilson interval and the JP interval “are very similar, and either may be used depending on taste”. However, the differences seen here (and the results we shall see below in Figs. 5–7) call this statement into question. See, for example, the lower limits for $n = 12$ and $x = 11$. Our belief is that, in a frequentist analysis, a method based on frequentist principles is more logically satisfactory than a method derived from a different approach to reasoning. So we emphasize the appropriateness of the Wilson approach.

5 Optimality criteria

We now consider how such an interval is to behave and how its performance might be evaluated. A upper confidence limit on π is a lower confidence limit on $1 - \pi$. So there is no loss of generality in focusing our discussion on the lower limit, $L \equiv L(X, \pi, n, \alpha)$. It is apparent that, in any reasonable method, $U \equiv L(n - X, \pi, n, \alpha)$.

Ideally, we would be able to define L such that $\Pr(L < \pi) = 1 - \alpha$ for all realistic π and n . However, the discrete nature of the binomial distribution means that this is not possible. Instead, a probability like $\Pr(L < \pi)$ as a function of π exhibits a sawtooth pattern as in Figure 2, (which depicts $\Pr(L_{\text{W}} \leq \pi)$ for $n = 16$ and $\alpha = 0.05$). Such a pattern typically shows anti-conservatism at some values of the parameters and conservatism at others. So we seek to balance the long-run loss of ‘truth status’ caused by anti-conservatism at some values of the parameters with the long-run loss of ‘information’ caused by conservatism at others.

Figure 2: The probability the lower Wilson limit L_{W} gives a true inference ‘ $\pi \geq \ell_{\text{W}}$ ’ for $n = 16$ and $\alpha = 0.05$

Statisticians have different views about balancing these considerations. The classical idea is that the confidence coefficient $\min_{\pi,n}\{\Pr(L < \pi)\}$ is to reach $1 - \alpha$. This is intellectually appealing, and this was the author’s view when introduced to statistical inference. However, the applied statistician also has an obligation to carry out an analysis that produces an informative inference. So the view I now hold (for this problem) is that the coverage probability can be smoothed by considering performance over a local range of values of the parameters, as in Newcombe [3] and elsewhere. However, my argument for integrating over π is not quite the same as the argument given by Newcombe, and I shall consider a different extent of smoothing also.

The inference drawn is “ $\pi \geq \ell$ ” where ℓ is the realization of L . If the inference is true, the amount of information it imparts about π is inversely related to the difference $\pi - \ell$. The requirements to make true inferences and informative inferences are, of course, in competition. The trick, and one of the concepts that differentiates inductive statistics from deductive mathematics, is to find the right balance.

5.1 Measuring anti-conservatism

Preliminaries

Let us consider initially the idea of performance in interval estimation. In the author’s opinion, the statistician’s first responsibility is to attempt to make inferences with (at least) the implied rate of truthfulness. This nominal rate needs to be understood and appreciated by the client. If there is a nominal level $1 - \alpha$ such that $k \equiv 1/\alpha$ is an integer then the client can easily relate to the idea that ‘one in every k ’ of the intervals he or she receives from statisticians will fail to contain the relevant parameter in the problems represented. This idea of a recognized failure rate gives meaning to the statement of reliability, e.g., “95%”, that accompanies any individual interval. This seems to me to be an important reason for the routine use of fixed tail probabilities and fixed confidence levels. Arguably, this idea of consistency and communicability is undervalued: there is merit in the use of conventional figures of Type I error, even if the original motivation for the particular convention was one of convenience.

Occasionally, a confidence-interval procedure with exact $1 - \alpha$ coverage generates a dataset S for which the associated ‘*conditional* confidence level’, say a_S , would differ from $1 - \alpha$. Thus, as with a ‘recognizable subset’ or ‘relevant subset’, it might be thought appropriate to quote a_S as the level of reliability of the inference if S arises. However, because the initial procedure is exact in the long run, the possibility that a_S is less than $1 - \alpha$ is balanced by the possibility that a_S is greater than $1 - \alpha$. So to require that we state the level of reliability as a_S when we had no prior knowledge of the dataset we were to observe seems to me to be a complication. Given that the client knows and accepts that the long-run ‘success-rate’ (or ‘truth-rate’) is the figure advertised, $1 - \alpha$, it seems better for him or her to remain ignorant of some theoretical detail in order to be able to continue to interpret the interval in the most helpful way. So our emphasis is very much on preserving and communicating the long-run success rate understood (correctly) by the client — which is the ethos of frequentist statistical inference.

Our context is the specification of an individual confidence limit. Although, the literal use of the term ‘coverage’ seems to require a finite interval, we will use it in the one-sided context also. This is, perhaps, an abuse of language, but stating a lower limit L is equivalent to stating the interval $[L, \infty)$, and the word ‘coverage’ could properly be applied to that interval. Thus, in what follows, we will also use the term ‘coverage’ in relation to the probability $\Pr(L \leq \pi)$.

Measure

The ideas just described apply to the estimation of a proportion π . Any client who receives a series of intervals in problems of this type will do so with values of π that differ to some extent, say π_1, π_2, \dots . The client’s interpretation of these intervals relies on a long-run concept, so it is appropriate to consider the performance of the method with values of π that are spread. The question is ‘spread by how much and with what weighting?’ There are a number of relevant considerations. For example, Newcombe and Nurminen [14] and Newcombe [3, Sec. 4.2.2] argue very reasonably that the minimum coverage probability with the Wilson method is experienced in a region of parameter-space where the method would not be used — where there is a small probability and a small sample size. Such ideas encourage them to smooth the kinds of curve seen in Fig. 2 over a window of π of extent ± 0.1 , e.g. [3, Figure 4.2]. Thus, in a one-tailed analysis, those authors would be comparing $1 - \alpha$ with the quantity $\frac{1}{0.2} \int_{\pi-0.1}^{\pi+0.1} \Pr\{L(p, n) \leq \pi \leq U(p, n)\} dp$. However, if we are prepared to accept a realized confidence interval at all then, presumably, we do not have any information that would subsequently alter the resulting inference. This suggests that, among potential values of π in the interval calculated, we have no prior reason to favour one potential value over another. Hence, we can justify smoothing over, say, half the width of the typical interval, $\approx 2\sqrt{\{\pi(1 - \pi)/n\}}$, and this will generally be at least as large as the ‘wavelength’ in the sawtooth pattern, which is approximately $1/n$. So, in our main results, we shall smooth over an interval of extent approximately $\pm 1/n$, which (for realistic n) is less than the extent ± 0.1 used by Newcombe and Nurminen in their two-sided context. Thus, in our one-sided problem, we will prefer to evaluate the quantity

$$C'(\pi; n, \alpha) \equiv \frac{n}{2} \int_{\pi-1/n}^{\pi+1/n} \Pr\{L(p, n) \leq \pi\} dp$$

for comparison with the ideal value, $1 - \alpha$.

So the idea of smoothing a coverage probability can be justified by arguing that the client’s idea of a success rate will relate to a series of non-identical problems with different values of the parameters. This applies with the sample size n as well as with π , so it also seems meaningful to smooth over n .¹ For fixed π , the points of discontinuity in the sawtooth vary with n , so averaging over a moderate range of n will lead to a considerably smoother function. Therefore, after integrating over the window of π , we shall also average over all sample sizes from $n_1 \equiv n - [0.1n]$ to $n_2 \equiv n + [0.1n]$ inclusive, where $[x]$ denotes the largest integer less than or equal to x .² Thus, the ordinate in the following graphs of coverage for sample size n is the quantity

$$C(\pi; n, \alpha) \equiv \frac{1}{n_2 - n_1 + 1} \sum_{m=n_1}^{n_2} C'(\pi; m, \alpha) \quad n_2, n_1 \equiv n \pm [0.1n].$$

(It could be argued that, for consistency, our method should be evaluated with the same degree of smoothing as that of previous authors. However, we are assessing the accuracy of a limit, not the accuracy of an interval. So the results are not directly comparable, and there would be little practical benefit from consistency in this instance.)

5.2 Measuring conservatism

If coverage of a procedure exceeds the advertised level $1 - \alpha$ then the procedure will be generating inferences that are not as informative as hoped for. However, because the present problem involves

¹The is perhaps not the case with *acceptance sampling* in industry, where inspectors typically study the same number of packages in each test.

²https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Floor_and_ceiling_functions (accessed 11 May 2022)

discrete variables, a large departure from $1 - \alpha$ does not necessitate a great loss of information. So we should not measure the level of conservatism by the difference $\Pr(L < \pi) - (1 - \alpha)$, and a different measure is appropriate. In interval estimation, the usual measure would be the mean width of the confidence interval, and in our single-sided problem the analogous measure is the mean value of $\pi - L$. However, it is debatable whether the occasions for which the inference is false should contribute to the figure quoted. So the measure of efficiency chosen here is the expected value of $\pi - L$ on the condition that $L < \pi$, $\mathcal{E}[\pi - L|L < \pi]$. (The common practice of evaluating efficiency by expected length is simplistic. If an interval fails to contain the parameter studied then the shortness of the interval seems to be a figure of debit, not a figure of merit. The limits of a short false interval will tend to be further from the true value of parameter than the limits of a long false interval — so the measure of efficiency must treat instances of coverage and non-coverage differently.)

6 Performance

6.1 Smoothed coverage and efficiency

The performances of the lower limits L_W , L_{AC} , L_{JP} , L_H , L_0 and L_{M3} were compared by evaluating the functions $C(\pi; n, \alpha)$ and $\mathcal{E}[\pi - L|L < \pi]$ for various sample sizes n and for $\alpha \in \{0.005, 0.01, 0.025, 0.05\}$. The integrals over π were approximated by simple summation of the contributions from the relevant values of π in the fine set $\{0, (0.001), 1\}$. Each procedure is equivariant in the sense that, by symmetry, the behaviour of the upper limit mirrors the behaviour of the lower limit as π is replaced by $1 - \pi$, so results for the upper limits can be inferred from the results presented here. The basic results are seen in Figures 3–6.

Figure 3 shows $C(\pi; n, \alpha)$ for the proposed limit L_{M3} and for the limits on which it is based, L_W and L_0 . In each panel there is a set of traces for each of $\alpha \in \{0.005, 0.01, 0.025, 0.05\}$. Consider, for example, the lowest three traces for $n = 10$. These show that for $n = 10$ and $\alpha = 0.05$ (i) the methods err on the side of anticonservatism when $\pi < 0.5$ and conservatism when $\pi > 0.5$, (ii) the error is considerably less for L_0 than for L_W and (iii) L_{M3} is better still. The same statements can be made for smaller α and larger n , with the advantage from using L_{M3} remaining but being diminished as n increases. The presence of a trend in the traces even for large n seems associated with the basic idea of approximating an asymmetric distribution by a symmetric one.

Figure 4 shows $C(\pi; n, \alpha)$ for L_{M3} , L_{AC} and the constrained Hall limit L_H for $n = 10, 30, 100$. The limit L_{AC} has a tendency to be more conservative than the Wilson limit. The limit L_H is based on results in asymptotic theory, but that is no guarantee of good performance, even with a value of n that might be considered large.

In the light of Figures 3–4, we conclude that the limit L_{M3} is more accurate than any of L_W , L_0 , L_{AC} and L_H . But our final answer for the initial evaluation of accuracy is taken from Figure 5, which shows $C(\pi; n, \alpha)$ for the proposed limit L_{M3} and the remaining limit L_{JP} . The limit L_{JP} is seen to be very slightly anti-conservative, to exhibit general flatness of slope, and to outperform L_{M3} in some situations. However, it exhibits a troublesome spike at $\pi \approx 7/n$. (See also Figure 7 to follow.) It could be preferred for $n \gtrsim 20$ when π was known to not be in the troublesome region. The general accuracy of L_{JP} when measured in this way is noteworthy given that it is derived in a quite different manner. Its structure and avoidance of the symmetric, normal, distribution means that it addresses the asymmetry of coverage more successfully as a general rule. Our view is that, provided it is interpreted as a frequentist procedure based on a heuristic tuning, it is worthy of use. However, if the use of L_{JP} is interpreted as a serious Bayesian procedure then — because the concept of ‘logical probability’ has been shown to be fundamentally flawed [7, 8, 9] — the result becomes misleading.

The limit L_H is not discussed further. Figure 6 shows $\mathcal{E}[\pi - L|L < \pi]$ for the five remaining

limits for $n = 10, 40$. There are various things to note. One is the comparative conservatism of L_{AC} at extreme values of π , and a second is the general similarity of the results for the other limits. The most important observation is that as π gets larger the inefficiency, as measured in this way, gets smaller, (even though the error in coverage probability $\Pr(L \leq \pi) - (1 - \alpha)$ might increase sharply on Figures 3–5. This corresponds to the point made in the text, which is that a method in a discrete problem can appear conservative probabilistically without being inefficient practically. We do not consider $\mathcal{E}[\pi - L | L < \pi]$ further.

Overall, the results exemplified in Figures 3–6 support the conclusion that the limits L_{M3} and U_{M3} are suitable for general use. Performance with these limits is noticeably better than with the Wilson limits and Agresti-Coull limits, and they are able to be written explicitly. The limits L_{JP} and U_{JP} seem applicable provided that they are not given Bayesian interpretations: (but see Figure 7).

Figure 3: Coverage probability for lower confidence limit L . The ordinate is $y = C(\pi; n, \alpha)$. Thick solid line L_{M3} . Dashed line L_0 . Dotted line L_W .

Figure 4: As in Figure 3. Thick solid line L_{M3} . Dot-dashed line L_{AC} . Solid line L_{HA} .

Figure 5: As in Figure 3. Thick solid line L_{M3} . Long-dashed line L_{JP} .

Figure 6: Inefficiency of the confidence limits. The ordinate is $y^* = \mathcal{E}[\pi - L | L < \pi]$. Thick solid line L_{M3} . Dashed line L_0 . Dotted line L_W . Dot-dashed line L_{AC} . Long-dashed line L_{JP} .

6.2 Tuning

We now consider the reasons for our choice of the function $f(X, n, \alpha) = L_0^{0.25+15\alpha}$ in defining L_{M3} . There are a number of factors.

- The basic limit L_0 improves on L_W , and there is further gain as $f(X, n, \alpha)$ begins to increase from zero.
- The random variable Y is only observable when the argument of the square-root function is non-negative. This is not guaranteed if $f(X, n, \alpha)$ is positive: some choices without solution have been observed when n is small. Nevertheless, exhaustive evaluations shows that a solution exists with $f(X, n, \alpha) = L_0^{0.25+15\alpha}$ for all $n \leq 200$ and all $\alpha \in \{0.005, 0.01, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1\}$.
- There is no need for X to appear as L_0 in the definition of $f(X, n, \alpha)$. Basing the definition on L_0 helped find a definition for which a solution existed everywhere.
- Setting $f(X, n, \alpha)$ larger than $L_0^{0.25+15\alpha}$ tended to produce a spike indicative of inadequate coverage near $\pi \sim 1 - 3/n$ for small n . The beginning of this is seen in the trace for L_{M3} with $n = 10$ and $\alpha = 0.05$ in Figures 3, 4 and 5, but the extent of this is tolerable at these settings. (Figure 7 shows results for small n and for $\alpha \in \{0.05, 0.1\}$. It shows that performance with L_{M3} is not as good with the unrealistic setting of $\alpha = 0.1$ if $n \lesssim 20$. We suggest that L_0 be used instead in such a situation. Figure 7 also shows problematic behaviour with L_{JP} with $\alpha = 0.05$ when n is small.)
- Using an exponent that is dependent on n and is not based on ‘round’ numbers might improve the performance slightly. But there is merit in simplicity.

Figure 7: Coverage probability for lower confidence limit L for small n and for $\alpha = 0.05$ (top) and $\alpha = 0.1$ (bottom). The ordinate is $y = C(\pi; n, \alpha)$. Thick solid line L_{M3} . Dashed line L_0 . Dotted line L_W . Dot-dashed line L_{AC} . Long-dashed line L_{JP} .

6.3 Intervals

Our focus has been on the performance of the individual limits L and U . However, we might also consider the performance of the corresponding nominal $1 - 2\alpha$ interval $I \equiv [L, U]$. The coverage probability of the interval is

$$\Pr(I \ni \pi) \equiv \Pr(L \leq \pi \leq U) = \Pr(L \leq \pi) + \Pr(U \geq \pi) - 1,$$

and the figure of coverage probability smoothed in the manner above is

$$C_I(\pi; n, 2\alpha) \equiv C(\pi; n, \alpha) + C(1 - \pi; n, \alpha) - 1.$$

Recall that the limits L_0 , L_{M3} and L_H were developed explicitly for one-tailed analysis, so the corresponding intervals I_0 , I_{M3} and I_H are, to some degree, artificial.

Fig. 8 shows $C_I(\pi; n, 2\alpha)$ for $n = 10, 20, 40$. Our attention is centred on the usual levels, $\alpha = 0.025$ and $\alpha = 0.005$, which correspond to nominal 95% and 99% intervals, but we also consider the unusual choice of $\alpha = 0.05$, given a 90% interval. We see that, if two-sided performance is all that is required:

- The JP interval is slightly anti-conservative for 95% and 90% intervals.
- The Wilson 95% and 90% intervals seems preferable.
- There is insignificant benefit from the use of the M3 interval, which develops under-coverage with 90% intervals.

We conclude that if asymmetry of coverage is not relevant and the ‘method of alternative moments’ is to be used with intervals then the more basic limits L_0 and U_0 offer a little more than L_{M3} and U_{M3} — but the Wilson limits are preferable for the usual setting of $1 - 2\alpha = 0.95$.

Figure 8: Coverage probability of interval $I \equiv [L, U]$, i.e., $\Pr(I \ni \pi : \pi \in [0, 1])$. The ordinate is $y = C_I(\pi; n, 2\alpha)$. Thick solid line I_{M3} . Dashed line I_0 . Dotted line I_W . Dot-dashed line I_{AC} . Long-dashed line I_{JP} .

6.4 Confidence coefficients

It seems appropriate in this problem to smooth the coverage probability over both π and n when evaluating the performances of a limit. However, it is still of interest to examine the probability $\min_{\pi} \{\Pr(L < \pi : \pi \in [0, 1])\}$, which is the *confidence coefficient* for $L \equiv L(n, \alpha)$ for the relevant parameters n and α . The confidence coefficients for the limits were evaluated by considering all values of π in the set $\{0, (0.001), 1\}$. Fig. 9 shows the results for $n = 5, \dots, 50$ with $\alpha = 0.05$ and $\alpha = 0.01$. We see, for example, that the confidence coefficient of the proposed limit L_{M3} is considerably greater than those of L_W and L_{JP} . (It is interesting to note that some limits display a ‘sawtooth’ pattern *with changing* n . This is not to be confused with a sawtooth pattern with changing π , as exemplified in Fig. 2, but it does relate to the question of whether smoothing over n is important.) Fig. 10 shows the corresponding confidence coefficients for nominal 95% and 99% intervals.

Figure 9: Confidence coefficient (c.c.) of limit L , i.e., $\min\{\Pr(L \leq \pi : \pi \in [0, 1])\}$. (a) 95% limit (b) 99% limit. Thick solid line L_{M3} . Dashed line L_0 . Dotted line L_W . Dot-dashed line L_{AC} . Long-dashed line L_{JP} .

Figure 10: Confidence coefficient (c.c.) of interval $I \equiv [L, U]$, i.e., $\min\{\Pr(I \ni \pi : \pi \in [0, 1])\}$. (a) 95% interval (b) 99% interval. Thick solid line I_{M3} . Dashed line I_0 . Dotted line I_W . Dot-dashed line I_{AC} . Long-dashed line I_{JP} .

7 Conclusion

Medical research involves the development of treatments that will only be applied if they have been demonstrated to be beneficial, and this involves the use of natural one-tailed reasoning. Therefore, it is important to focus on the calculation of accurate individual confidence limits. Any inference about an unknown fixed parameter can be reduced to a pair of inequalities, one involving an upper bound and one a lower bound. So the element of a practical inference is a one-sided analysis.

This paper has presented two new individual $1 - \alpha$ confidence limits for a binomial proportion π when observing a random number of ‘successes’, X , in n independent trials. The limits are obtained from the limits of the Wilson interval [4] by matching the first and *third* moments of normal and binomial distributions, in what might be called a ‘method of alternative moments’. The basic limits obtained are the limits L_0 and U_0 given by (7) and (8), but the limits proposed for general use are the limits L_{M3} and U_{M3} given by (9) and (10). The only existing limits that appear competitive are those obtained when using the Jeffrey’s prior distribution as a heuristic tool. The new limits can be written explicitly.

Appendix: Wilson’s analysis

In the problem of finding a lower confidence limit for π , the statistician seeks to identify the minimum value of π that, through the associated sampling distribution with unknown standard error $\sqrt{\pi(1 - \pi)/n}$, could reasonably have given rise to the observation $p \equiv x/n$. The Wilson limit L_W is derived by such a thought process, which involves a probability integral, not a likelihood function. This is evident in the concise paper of Wilson [4], whose context is two-tailed estimation and who gives the relevant ideas in just one page of text. Agresti and Caffo [6] suggest that Wilson be recognised for his significant contributions to statistics. Here, we argue that the designation ‘score interval’, which is sometimes used to describe the Wilson interval, fails to represent one of these contributions.³

The following two ‘quotations’ reproduce the relevant paragraphs in Wilson’s paper, with some of the wording and notation updated. Wilson begins by observing that typical contemporary inference would involve calculating a standard error at the point estimate p and making the unknown constant π the subject of an ‘elliptical’, i.e., unclear and roundabout, non-trivial probability statement. He then turns this vague understanding on its head in what is now standard frequentist thinking. His brevity and use of colloquial language is refreshing.

Probable inference (Usual). If there be observed a certain proportion p in a sample of n and if the corresponding standard deviation $\sqrt{p(1 - p)/n} = \sigma_p$ be computed, the common statement of probable inference is to say that: The probability that the true value of the proportion π lies outside the limits $p - z\sigma_p$ and $p + z\sigma_p$ is less than or equal to P_z

Strictly speaking, the usual statement of probable inference given above is elliptical. Really, the chance that the true probability π lies outside a specified range is either 0 or 1; for π actually lies within that range or not. It is the observed rate p which has a greater or less chance of lying within a certain interval of the true rate π . If the observer has had the hard luck to have observed a relatively rare event and to have based his inference thereon, he may be fairly wide of the mark.

Immediately, Wilson continues:

³Elsewhere, the Wilson limits have been unhelpfully referred to as Agresti-Coull limits. <https://www.itl.nist.gov/div898/software/dataplot/refman2/auxillar/agcoulci.htm> (accessed 2 Nov. 2021)

Probable inference (Improved). A better way to proceed is to reason as follows: There is some proportion π , and the associated standard deviation is $\sqrt{\pi(1-\pi)/n} = \sigma$. For a value of p outside the limits $\pi - z\sigma$ and $\pi + z\sigma$, the probability that an observation as bad as p will occur is less than or equal to P_z . This form of statement throws the emphasis upon the fallibility of a particular observation in respect to being typical of a general situation.

It is still possible to state the criterion in terms of the observed proportion p , for the equation $(p - \pi)^2 = z^2\pi(1 - \pi)/n$ is quadratic in π and may be solved to find π . If $z^2/n = t$, the solution is

$$\pi = \frac{p + t/2}{1 + t} \pm \frac{\sqrt{pqt + t^2/4}}{1 + t}.$$

The rule then may be stated as: If the true value of the probability π lies outside the range

$$\frac{p + t/2}{1 + t} - \frac{\sqrt{pqt + t^2/4}}{1 + t} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{p + t/2}{1 + t} + \frac{\sqrt{pqt + t^2/4}}{1 + t},$$

the chance of having such hard luck as to have made an observation as bad as p is less than or equal to P_z . And this form of statement is not elliptical. It is the proper form of probable inference.

Wilson does not mention likelihood, and he makes no appeal to the idea of a ‘score test’, (which is derived from the idea of the likelihood function and which dates from the 1940s). Instead, Wilson simply engages in honest and straightforward thinking. He hints at the Copernican, frequentist, idea that our observations are distributed about the underlying reality, not *vice versa*. We suggest that the term ‘score’ not be used when describing his interval. Would it be too much to name it the ‘Wilson common-sense interval’?

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